

Table 2. Reactions^a of R243-3223, IR36, and 3 other varieties to bacterial leaf blight, blast, sheath rot, and gall midge. Madhya Pradesh, India.

Strain or variety	Mean score			Blast ^c 1983	Sheath rot ^d 1983	Gall midge (% silver shoots) 1984
	Bacterial leaf blight					
	1982	1983	1984			
R243-3223	3.6	3.0	2.9	1.8	3.0	4.0
IR36	4.7	5.0	5.3	—	—	6.8
TNI	7.0	7.2	8.9	5.0	—	62.5
Jaya	5.3	7.0	6.5	4.5	5.5	58.2
Safri 17	5.8	6.3	5.4	—	—	37.6

^aBy the Standard evaluation system for rice scale. ^b0 = no incidence, 9 = 51-100%. ^cMean of 4 locations: Almore, Cuttack, Ponnampet, and Semliguda. 0 = no lesions, 9 = all leaves dead. ^dMean of 2 locations: Faizabad and Pusa. 0 = no incidence, 9 = 51-100%.

broadcast sowing and higher drought tolerance than IR36. Its excellent tolerance for bacterial blight, gall midge, blast, and sheath rot makes it distinctly superior to Safri 17 (Table 2). Also, the new line is 15 d earlier than Safri 17, so that it frequently escapes terminal drought. ☞

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Performance trials of short-duration rice varieties at TNRRI

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Performance trials of short duration, high yielding rice varieties were conducted at TNRRI during 1984 kharif. Seven varieties from IRRRI, three from Tamil Nadu, and one from Sri Lanka were evaluated in a randomized block design with three replications.

Seedlings were spaced 15 cm between rows and 10 cm within rows. Fertilizer was 75-38-38 kg NPK/ha. Plots were free from insects and diseases from planting to harvest.

AD85001 and IR58 flowered earliest, 72 and 71 d after seeding (DAS). IR62

Performance of short-duration rice varieties at TRRI, India, 1984 kharif.

Variety	Source	Height (cm)	Days to 50% flowering	Yield (t/ha)
AD85001	Tamil Nadu	85	72	4.8
TKM 9	Tamil Nadu	91	86	5.8
ADT36	Tamil Nadu	93	84	4.8
BG367-4	Sri Lanka	98	82	6.0
IR36	IRRI	81	86	4.7
IR50	IRRI	89	82	4.6
IR52	IRRI	92	86	5.1
IR56	IRRI	96	82	5.3
IR58	IRRI	86	71	3.0
IR60	IRRI	92	82	5.1
IR62	IRRI	94	84	4.9
IR64	IRRI	92	86	5.1
				CD 0.3
				CV 7.5

was latest, 89 DAS. Other varieties flowered between 82 and 86 DAS. Varietal height ranged from 85 cm (AD85001) to 98 cm (BG367-4).

BC367-4, the Sri Lankan culture, yielded 6.0 t/ha, surpassing all other

varieties. IRRRI varieties IR52, IR50, IR60, and IR64 recorded more than 5 t/ha (see table). These varieties will be studied in multilocation and adaptive research trials in 1986 kharif. ☞

ACK-5, a new variety for Western Maharashtra, India

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Rice variety ACK-5, released in 1985, is derived from a cross between tall type D-6-2-2 and stable high yielding semidwarf IR8. The new variety has medium height (65 cm) and matures in 120 d. Its seed has a 20-d dormancy.

It is nonlodging, and is suitable for

Performance of ACK-5 in various trials. Maharashtra, India.

Trial	Year	Mean yield (t/ha)			% increase over check
		ACK-5	Jaya	RDN185-2	
Initial evaluation trial (ET)	1976-78	2.6	2.3	—	11.0
Multilocation trials	1983-84	4.5	—	3.9	14.0
Adaptive trials	1983	3.6	—	3.4	6.3
Cultivator fields	1984	3.4	—	3.2	7.4

direct sowing as well as transplanting. It is tolerant of moisture stress and iron chlorosis.

Its grain is short, bold, and coarse with acceptable cooking qualities, suitable for preparing flaked and puffed

rice. Yield is 4-6 t/ha under direct-sown conditions and 44.5 t/ha under transplanted conditions. Yield data in various trials are shown in the table. ACK-5 is moderately susceptible to blast and susceptible to bacterial blight. ☞